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MOOSE Framework Enhancements to Support Generic Constructive Solid Geometry Representations

Shikhar Kumar¹, Kalin Kiesling¹, Guillaume Giudicelli², Logan Harbour², Emily Shemon¹

¹Argonne National Laboratory, 9700 S. Cass Ave., Lemont, IL 60439;

²Idaho National Laboratory, 1955 Fremont Ave., Idaho Falls, ID 83415

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ABSTRACT

Monte Carlo simulations are increasingly being integrated into deterministic multiphysics workflows, which require equivalent problem domains to be defined using inherently different conventions and practices. The ability to switch between finite element mesh representations (used by many deterministic methods) and constructive solid geometry (CSG) representations (used by Monte Carlo methods) can alleviate significant user burden. MOOSE already contains extensive meshing capabilities that streamline the generation of finite element meshes for nuclear reactor analysis. Recently, the MOOSE framework has been extended to support the conversion from the MOOSE mesh-based input to an equivalent CSG representation through the newly defined `--csg-only` command line option. Invoking this option generates a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) output file that contains the generic definitions of CSG surfaces, cells, and universes that define the geometric domain, which can then be connected to the geometry definitions of downstream Monte Carlo codes. Support for CSG representation has been extended to the Reactor Geometry Mesh Builder (RGMB) mesh generators, allowing for seamless conversion to CSG from common reactor finite element mesh input specifications. This workflow was successfully demonstrated to convert the Advanced Burner Test Reactor (ABTR) core from the MOOSE input to a CSG representation that is analogous to the finite element mesh representation.

Keywords: MOOSE, multiphysics, Constructive Solid Geometry, Monte Carlo, finite element method

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in high performance computing and numerical modeling have allowed multiphysics simulations to become a practical and indispensable tool for high-fidelity nuclear reactor analysis, enabling detailed descriptions of coupled physics effects to determine reactor performance and safety. Typically, analysts looking to run multiphysics simulations are expected to set up problems across different physics solvers, understanding the nuances, requirements, and limitations of each individual physics code. Multiphysics Object-Oriented Simulation Environment (MOOSE) is a state of the art, open source framework foundation to enable high-fidelity coupled multiphysics simulation for reactor analysis [1]. Under the Department of Energy Office of Nuclear Energy Advanced Modeling and Simulation (DOE-NEAMS) program [2], significant improvements have been made to MOOSE to generate the required input finite element meshes for nuclear reactor geometries [3, 4] needed for by finite element-based MOOSE solvers. The finite element mesh generation process requires discretizing the input domain into a collection of discretized mesh elements over which the physics problem of interest is solved.

In recent years, Monte Carlo reactor physics calculations have increasingly become part of these multiphysics workflows. Monte Carlo simulations can provide a pathway for cross section generation for deterministic reactor physics codes or an avenue for generating high-fidelity reference solutions. This type of workflow is seen commonly between the Shift Monte Carlo code [5] and the MOOSE-based

Griffin deterministic code [6]. Monte Carlo codes can also replace deterministic methods as the driver for reactor physics calculations when coupled to other physics solvers within the MOOSE ecosystem, as seen in the Cardinal code [7].

The increased popularity of Monte Carlo codes in multiphysics workflows, however, poses a challenge for users in that Monte Carlo codes represent the geometric domain in a way that is fundamentally different from how finite element meshes are defined. Namely, Monte Carlo codes use Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) to define the spatial domain, and construction of this geometry representation can be a complex and tedious task that requires users to be familiar with the specific syntax and conventions imposed by the Monte Carlo code of choice. Users looking to run coupled simulations relying on MOOSE codes and Monte Carlo codes would have to define multiple equivalent geometry representations, a process that is cumbersome and prone to user error due to the inherent duplication of effort required to represent the input domain. This work describes recent improvements to the MOOSE framework to enable automated conversion from mesh-based MOOSE input to Monte Carlo CSG representation, thereby improving workflow efficiency, reducing potential for human error, and removing barriers to entry to incorporate Monte Carlo simulations into deterministic workflows.

2. MOOSE FRAMEWORK IMPLEMENTATION

The process in MOOSE to generate CSG representations from finite element mesh representations relies directly on the geometrical specifications defined in the MOOSE mesh input file rather than recreating the CSG representation directly from the finite element mesh produced by MOOSE. Using the input specifications directly maintains geometric accuracy, as the input file has the exact geometric information about the underlying spatial domain and structure of repeated regions in lattices, whereas this information would be much more difficult to recover by inspecting the output mesh. Additionally, it minimizes the number of surfaces in the resulting CSG definition compared to duplicating a faceted mesh representation.

As an example, Figure 1 shows a hexagonal pin cell with two inner concentric circles, as well as a coarsely defined finite element mesh representation of the same pin cell. By inspecting the mesh input file directly, MOOSE can determine the exact radii of the circular regions and pitch of the outer hexagon in order to define the CSG representation of the pin cell as shown in the right image of Figure 1. On the other hand, the finite element mesh representation shown on the left image of Figure 1 requires each region to be discretized into separate mesh elements, making it more challenging to recover information about the radii of the rings and the pitch of the hexagonal pin as those quantities are only implicitly featured in the mesh.

Figure 1. An example of a pin cell using a finite element mesh (left) and CSG representation (right).

The output CSG model generated by MOOSE is both accurate and consistent in its geometric representation, regardless of how the finite element mesh discretization is defined. Moreover, each CSG region can be represented by the minimum number of surfaces, and does not suffer from the discretization errors that would normally be present in finite element meshes that represent curved surfaces.

2.1. Introduction of the MOOSE CSGBase Framework

This section discusses some of the lower-level implementation details related to construction of the finite element representation and equivalent CSG representation in MOOSE. As a brief introduction to the MOOSE mesh generator system, the final output finite element mesh is constructed by forming a direct acyclic graph of `MeshGenerator` objects, all specified within the `[Mesh]` block of the MOOSE input file. Each `MeshGenerator` object is responsible for either constructing a finite element mesh from scratch in a specific way (e.g. define a pin cell), or modifying an existing element mesh to build on top of what has already been defined (e.g. place pin cell objects into a lattice). Within MOOSE, each `MeshGenerator` has a `generate()` method that explicitly defines the meshing operations that should occur during each step of the finite element mesh generation stage.

The process for defining an equivalent CSG representation is built on top of this mesh generator system. Each `MeshGenerator` object has an optional `generateCSG()` method that can be defined to generate the equivalent CSG representation. This method contains the specific CSG operations needed to produce the equivalent CSG object as the finite element mesh constructed by the `generate()` method. These routines are called in the same order between `MeshGenerators`, using the same dependency resolution as the mesh generation.

In order to support the conversion of mesh-based input in MOOSE to CSG representations, the back-end of the MOOSE framework was updated by defining a new `CSGBase` framework. This framework serves as a new application programming interface (API) to facilitate definition of CSG-based objects, and holds all CSG components needed to represent the underlying geometry. Developers use this `CSGBase` framework to define the CSG operations that need to occur within the `generateCSG()` method of each `MeshGenerator`.

2.2. Components of the CSGBase Framework

A number of additional classes are created to represent the CSG components that can be created or modified within the `CSGBase` framework:

- `CSGSurface` Represents a surface used to define the spatial extent of the region of a `CSGCell` (described below). MOOSE natively supports the definition of basic surface types such as planes, spheres, and axis-aligned cylinders. In addition, it provides the ability to define custom surfaces based on user needs (e.g. a torus for fusion applications), so that applications may create a specific surface type in their `MeshGenerator` that is not currently supported within MOOSE's main framework.
- `CSGRegion` Represents a CSG region, which is a space defined by boolean operations applied to surfaces and other regions. These boolean operations include halfspaces, unions, intersections, and complements. The resulting region is used to defined the domain of a `CSGCell` (described below).
- `CSGCell` Represents a CSG cell, defined as a region and a fill. Four types of cell fills are supported: void, material, universe, and lattice. Currently, material fills are not connected to any MOOSE material definitions, and are represented as a placeholder name. It is up to the end user to specify the compositions that correspond to each material name.
- `CSGUniverse` Represents a CSG universe, which is a collection of cells that can be used as a fill for other cells or used in a repeated manner, such as in a lattice.

- `CSGLattice` Represents a CSG lattice, which is a patterned array of CSG universe objects. Currently, 2D hexagonal and Cartesian lattices are supported by this class. Similar to the `CSGSurface` class, any custom lattice type can also be defined using this class.

Returning to the example shown in Figure 1, the `generateCSG()` method for defining the pin cell begins by creating the two cylindrical surfaces to represent each radial ring, as well as each of the six planar surfaces required to enclose the outer hexagonal boundary. Each of the three distinct radial regions in Figure 1 is then represented as a cell, and these three cells are combined into a single root universe. Each surface, cell, and universe is constructed by making the appropriate calls to the methods in the `CSGBase` framework. Since this is a 2D pin cell example, the surfaces defined within `CSGBase` are infinite in the axial dimension. However, additional planar surfaces can be defined to represent extruded geometries.

2.3. Usage and JSON Output Specifications

CSG generation is invoked through the command line when calling MOOSE by specifying the `--csg-only` flag, similar to the `--mesh-only` flag called to generate an Exodus file that represents the finite element mesh for the underlying problem. In order for `--csg-only` to work with the input file, every `MeshGenerator` called within the `[Mesh]` block must have a `generateCSG()` method defined. Importantly, from a performance perspective, this command line option bypasses finite element generation in favor of populating metadata to represent key data that might need to be retrieved by downstream `MeshGenerator` objects [8]. This avoids unnecessary finite element mesh object creation during the CSG generation process.

Running `--csg-only` on a compatible MOOSE input file produces a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file containing the complete generic CSG definition of the mesh input file. It is important here to note that this geometry description is defined in a generic manner, meaning that the data present in the JSON file fully describes the CSG geometry without any Monte Carlo code-specific syntax. The generic CSG representation allows maximum flexibility rather than requiring that a specific Monte Carlo code be used in order to leverage the conversion tool. Any Monte Carlo code developer can elect to develop an interface to take MOOSE's generic CSG description and convert to its own code-specific syntax.

The full JSON output for an 2D pin cell definition equivalent to what is shown in Figure 1 can be found in Appendix A. This file lists all the surfaces, cells, and universes needed to define the pin cell. Even for this relatively simple geometry, a large number of CSG components need to be defined to properly create the 2D pin cell, which highlights the complexity and difficulty associated with manually defining large models. This generic JSON output file can then be used as a starting point to define the input geometry for the downstream Monte Carlo codes.

3. DEMONSTRATION CASES

As a practical demonstration case, the `generateCSG()` method was defined for the Reactor Geometry Mesh Builder (RGMB), a subset of mesh generators within the MOOSE Reactor module that streamlines mesh generation for conventional Cartesian and hexagonal lattice-based reactor geometries [9]. This includes `PinMeshGenerator`, `AssemblyMeshGenerator`, and `CoreMeshGenerator`, allowing for full-core structured lattice geometries to be easily converted from finite element representation to CSG representation.

For this example, an existing RGMB-based mesh input file for the full-core Advanced Burner Test Reactor (ABTR) [10] was used to generate the equivalent CSG representation for the output mesh. The mesh representation is an extruded hexagonal core with a mixture of heterogeneous (pin-resolved) and homogeneous subassembly regions. Running `--csg-only` on the MOOSE mesh input file produces a JSON output file that contains the CSG definition of the problem. A custom script was then used to convert the JSON output file of this pin cell to OpenMC syntax [11] and plotted within OpenMC to confirm correctness of the CSG representation. These plots are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Representation of ABTR core in CSG, plotted in OpenMC as an XY slice (left) and XZ slice (right). The OpenMC input syntax and plots are generated from a custom script that operates on the output JSON file that is produced when running `--csg-only` on the RGMB mesh input file.

It should be emphasized here the same input file used to create the CSG representation can be used to generate the finite element mesh representation as well. To illustrate this point, Figure 3 shows the output finite element mesh when running `--mesh-only` on the input RGMB mesh file. Regardless of how the finite element mesh is discretized into its constituent elements, the CSG geometry representation shown in Figure 2 will define the spatial domain using the minimum number of surfaces required derived from the user input. For users looking to incorporate coupled multiphysics workflows between MOOSE finite element solvers and Monte Carlo solvers, this tool therefore serves to alleviate user burden, reduce time for model generation, and ensure consistency between geometry definitions for finite element-based and Monte Carlo-based simulations.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work introduces new functionality in MOOSE to create generalized and automated processes for creating CSG representations from MOOSE geometry input to support users looking to interface with Monte Carlo codes within their analysis workflows, such as multigroup cross section generation for deterministic neutronics calculations, generation of neutronics reference results, or multiphysics analysis relying on Monte Carlo simulations to model reactor physics feedback effects. To this end, a new `--csg-only` command line option has been added to MOOSE to generate a generic CSG representation, with a new CSGBase framework to support code development of how exactly each MeshGenerator should define the equivalent CSG representation for a given MOOSE mesh input file.

As CSG model generation is a complex and tedious task, this work serves to reduce barriers to entry for running Monte Carlo simulations by reducing model generation time, avoiding human error from defining Monte Carlo geometries, and automatically ensuring consistency between finite element mesh representation and CSG representation. This new capability was demonstrated for the 3D full-core ABTR core, showing that equivalent CSG and finite element element mesh definitions for this example

Figure 3. Representation of ABTR core as a finite element mesh, plotted in Paraview [12] as an XY slice (left) and XZ slice (right).

could be generated by invoking the `--csg-only` and `--mesh-only` command line options respectively from a common mesh input file.

Currently, the CSGBase framework is implemented within the main MOOSE framework. However, to facilitate the connection to external Monte Carlo codes such as Shift, future work includes taking the CSGBase framework out of MOOSE and supporting it as an external library that will be available by both MOOSE and the Monte Carlo codes for direct use. This will allow the Monte Carlo codes to easily use the existing methods within CSGBase when processing the generic CSG model through one of two of the following coupling options. The first option for coupling the framework to a Monte Carlo code is to use a JSON object or file layer as an intermediate step. The second option for connecting to a Monte Carlo code is direct in-memory coupling using the generated CSGBase object directly, bypassing the JSON object layer. Within the DOE NEAMS program, Shift will be connected to MOOSE via the first coupling option as a near-term implementation, while aiming to develop a more robust in-memory coupling in the long term. It should be noted that this framework is considered Monte Carlo code-agnostic, and as such these coupling methods could be used for connection to other Monte Carlo codes as well.

Additionally, adding CSG generation support for a wider range of MeshGenerator types and the ability to represent engineering units and typical CSG transformations such as translations and rotations is also planned. Finally, we hope to generalize the definitions of material zones within the CSG representation to also be able to handle arbitrary tally and depletion zones as well.

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APPENDIX A. SAMPLE JSON OUTPUT FILE FROM MOOSE CSG GENERATION

```
{
  "cells": {
    "pin1_cell_radial_0": {
      "fill": "rgmb_region_1", "filltype": "CSG_MATERIAL",
      "region_infix": "-pin1_radial_ring_0", "region_postfix": ["pin1_radial_ring_0", "-"],
    },
    "pin1_cell_radial_1": {
      "fill": "rgmb_region_2",
      "filltype": "CSG_MATERIAL",
      "region_infix": "(-pin1_radial_ring_1 & ~(-pin1_radial_ring_0))",
      "region_postfix": ["pin1_radial_ring_1", "-", "pin1_radial_ring_0", "-", "~", "&"]
    },
    "pin1_cell_radial_2": {
      "fill": "rgmb_region_3",
      "filltype": "CSG_MATERIAL",
      "region_infix": "(+pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_0 & +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_1 & "
        "+pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_2 & +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_3 & "
        "+pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_4 & +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_5 & ~(-pin1_radial_ring_1))",
      "region_postfix": ["pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_0", "+", "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_1", "+", "&",
        "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_2", "+", "&", "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_3", "+",
        "&", "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_4", "+", "&", "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_5",
        "+", "&", "pin1_radial_ring_1", "-", "~", "&"]
    },
    "pin1_void_cell": {
      "fill": "",
      "filltype": "VOID",
      "region_infix": "
        ~(+pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_0 & +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_1 & +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_2 "
        "& +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_3 & +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_4 & +pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_5)",
      "region_postfix": ["pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_0", "+", "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_1", "+", "&",
        "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_2", "+", "&", "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_3",
        "+", "&", "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_4", "+", "&",
        "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_5", "+", "&", "~"]
    }
  },
  "surfaces": {
    "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_0": {
      "coefficients": {"a": -0.5, "b": -0.866025, "c": 0.0, "d": -0.710315},
      "type": "CSG::CSGPlane"
    },
    "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_1": {
      "coefficients": {"a": 0.5, "b": -0.866025, "c": 0.0, "d": -0.710315},
      "type": "CSG::CSGPlane"
    },
    "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_2": {
      "coefficients": {"a": 1.0, "b": 0.0, "c": 0.0, "d": -0.710315},
      "type": "CSG::CSGPlane"
    },
    "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_3": {
      "coefficients": {"a": 0.5, "b": 0.866025, "c": 0.0, "d": -0.710315},
      "type": "CSG::CSGPlane"
    },
    "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_4": {
      "coefficients": {"a": -0.5, "b": 0.866025, "c": 0.0, "d": -0.710315},
      "type": "CSG::CSGPlane"
    },
    "pin1_radial_duct_2_surf_5": {
      "coefficients": {"a": -1.0, "b": 0.0, "c": 0.0, "d": -0.710315},
      "type": "CSG::CSGPlane"
    },
    "pin1_radial_ring_0": {
      "coefficients": {"r": 1.0, "x0": 0.0, "y0": 0.0}, "type": "CSG::CSGZCylinder"
    },
    "pin1_radial_ring_1": {
      "coefficients": {"r": 2.0, "x0": 0.0, "y0": 0.0}, "type": "CSG::CSGZCylinder"
    }
  },
  "universes": {
    "ROOT_UNIVERSE": {
      "cells": [
        "pin1_cell_radial_0", "pin1_cell_radial_1", "pin1_cell_radial_2", "pin1_void_cell"
      ],
      "root": true
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 4. Sample output JSON file for pin cell defined in Figure 1.